

An Investigation into the Conduct of Senior Secondary Certificate Examination (SSCE) in Special Centres of Adamawa State

*James Simon Bahago¹, Lois Ibrahim Swandun² & Hope Garba³

¹ Department of Biology, National Teachers' Institute, Kaduna, Katari Study Centre, Kaduna State, Nigeria.

^{2,3} Government Secondary School, Romi, Kaduna State Ministry of Education, Kaduna State, Nigeria.

*Corresponding author: [James Simon Bahago](mailto:sbjames2009@gmail.com)

Department of Biology, National Teachers' Institute, Kaduna, Katari Study Centre, Kaduna State, Nigeria.

Email: sbjames2009@gmail.com

Abstract

This study is an investigation into the conduct of Senior Secondary Certificate Examination (SSCE) in Special Centres of Adamawa State. The study put up three objectives and four research questions to guide the study. The study adopted survey research design type and sampled 240 respondents from 5 Local Government Areas across the state. The data collection instrument adopted was the 4 Likert Scale. The study found out that; examination malpractice is carried out in special examination centres in Adamawa State because of the premium placed on the examination in determining the future ambition of students and employers. The study also found that some of the factors affecting perceived to be affecting the free conduct of the examination included; lack of support from school principals and untimely payment of examiners and invigilators remunerations. The study therefore recommended for the prompt payment of the allowances of examiners and invigilators. More so, the study recommended for the training and retraining of school managers and examiners on examination ethics.

Keywords: SSCE, Special Centres, Examination Malpractice, Examiners.

Introduction

The Senior Secondary Certificate Examination (SSCE) in Nigeria is a summative public examination being conducted by two examination bodies: The West African Examinations Council (WAEC) and the National Examinations Council (NECO). The Senior Secondary Certificate Examination (SSCE) is written at the end of the third year of Senior Secondary schooling. The examination is a standardised high-stake examination (Agwu et al., 2022). The outcome of which determines to a very great extent an individual's chance of being admitted into higher institution of learning or paid employment (Afolabi, 2018). This perhaps could explain the reason why candidates, schools, government at Federal and state levels, parents, employers, institutions of higher learning and other stakeholders place high premium on the very importance of this examination. There is therefore agreement in literature that examination malpractice is perpetrated more often in standardised than during school-based examinations (Agwu et al., 2023). This could be attributed to the apparently higher level of importance attached to the SSCE by the Nigerian society. The functions that the SSCE performs in the Nigerian society are similar to the functions of public examinations anywhere in the world. These functions include selection/admission into higher institution or course of study and certification after the successful completion of a programme of study (Onyedinefu, 2019). The outcomes of public examinations like the Nigerian SSCE, also help employers in taking job placement decisions, public examinations also help in taking decisions as vital as those to be employed into paid employments and also for taking promotion decision (Omonijo, 2011).

Examination malpractice could simply be regarded as any deliberate act of wrong doing, contrary to the rules of examinations designed to give a candidate an undue advantage (Oko & Adie, 2016). No wonder examination malpractice is today one of the major ills in Nigeria's education system. Onyedinefu (2019) investigation via BusinessDay Newspaper show that while several reasons have been given for the rise of this menace, centres which disguise as tutorial centres are in fact centres for massive examination malpractices. More worrisome is the proliferation of these centers called 'miracle centres'. Most streets across Nigeria are today littered with their banners and posters luring students with

inscriptions assuring them of credits, while concerned authorities remain numb. Examination malpractice is not restricted to the examination venue alone but is also perpetrated before, during or after the administration of an examination. Examination malpractice makes candidates score unreachable by inflating the scores of those who cheat and thus enhance their chances of gaining admission at expense of those that might be better, where such happened without anybody detecting, the validity of the examination becomes questionable, Uzochukwu (2015). Too large population of candidates among others creates monitoring/supervision problem, which in turn gives a more relaxed atmosphere for the perpetration of malpractice on examinations.

The outcomes of researches have also supported the statement that examination malpractices are not new phenomena in Nigeria. The situation is similar elsewhere in the world (Agwu et al., 2023, Agwu et al., 2022 and Oko & Adie, 2016). The disturbing aspect of it is that the incidence is increasing and the desperation with which the perpetrators now pursue it is worrisome. It is widespread among candidates and has also been perpetrated by some examination officials (Uzochukwu, 2015).

Despite the intervention of the Federal Government, Agwu et al., (2023) confirmed that many unscrupulous examiners contribute to examination malpractices. In addition, examination bodies lack disciplinary control over teachers and non-staff, poor sitting arrangement, and lack of moral probity among some people handling and administering examinations all contribute to examination fraud.

Though there has been much in the literature on the assessment of public examination in Nigeria. There has been increase call to continue to carry out fresh research on the manner in which SSCE examination is executed. This became necessary as a result of continuing quest to provide lasting solution to this problem. It is on this background that effort is being made by the researcher to; Investigation into the Conduct of SSCE Examination in Special Centres of Adamawa State.

Statement of the Problem

Educational evaluation is paramount that accorded its deserved recognition in every nation. To ensure standard in education, effort must be geared towards ensuring its conduct is carried out in accordance and with effectiveness. In Nigeria, the SSCE examination is aimed at evaluation of students before transition to tertiary institutions. The Senior School Certificate Examinations (SSCE) in Nigeria have been a focus of discussion both by academics and the media. The discussion is on the conduct of the Senior School Certificate Examinations and rampant examination malpractice, late release of students' results, cancellation of results and poor performance of candidates (Yoloye, 2011). This array of problems and accusations calls for a continuous and thorough evaluation of the public examination system in Nigeria.

In view of the array of problems that keep rising from the conduct of public examinations, this study therefore carried out an investigation into the conduct of Senior School Certificate Examination in special centres of Adamawa State.

Objectives of the Study

The specific objectives of the study are;

- i. To investigate the conduct of Senior Secondary School Examination (SSCE) and rampant examination malpractice in Special Centres.
- ii. To identify the perceived factors affecting the proper conduct of SSCE as perceived by students and teachers
- iii. Investigate the reasons for special examination centres.

Research Questions

The following research questions were formulated:

- i. What are the factors affecting the conduct of SSCE as perceived by teachers and students?
- ii. How conducive are examination centres to students writing examination?
- iii. Do invigilators perceived their remuneration as adequate and promptly paid?
- iv. Do teachers/students perceive SSCE invigilation as effectively carried out?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study adopted a survey method of research design which estimates are drawn from a sample of particular population. Thereafter, data obtained from the sample represented the view of the entire population. This method is important because it deals with the classification of data such that it limits generalization to the particular group observed and conclusion is not extended to other groups beside the observed group.

Population of the Study

The Population of the Study consisted of the entire teachers and Students in all the Selected Secondary Schools in Mubi, Hong, Song, Yola North, Yola South, and Girei Local Government Area of Adamawa State.

Sample and Sampling Techniques

The Sample and Sampling techniques used for the study consisted of simple random sampling, which was used to select 120 teachers and 120 Students, making up a total population of 240 respondents sampled from the 12 selected secondary schools. The breakdown of the sample of the study is shown in the table below:

Table 1: Sample Frame

S/N	Local Government	School	Teachers	Students	Total
1	Hong	Government Day secondary School Shangui	10	10	20
		Government Secondary School Hong.	10	10	20
2	Song	Government Secondary School Song.	10	10	20
		Future Hope Secondary School Song.	10	10	20
3	Mubi	Government Day Secondary School Mubi.	10	10	20
		Abubakar Isah Academy Mubi.	10	10	20
4	Yola North	General Murtala Mohammed College Yola.	10	10	20
5.	Yola South	Government Day Secondary School Doubeli.	10	10	20
		Aliyu Mustapha College Yola.	10	10	20
		Government Science and Technical college Yola	10	10	20
		Government Day Secondary School Bajabure.	10	10	20
6.	Girei	Government Day Secondary School Vunoklang.	10	10	20
Total			120	120	240

Source: Field work, 2025

Instrument for Data Collection

The instrument used for the collection of data was questionnaire. The questionnaire was constructed by the researcher under the supervision of his supervisor. It consisted of four (4) Likert scale type for the response as follows:

SA: Strongly Agree = 4 point

A: Agree = 3 point

SD: Strongly Disagree = 2 point

D: Disagree = 1 point

Method of Data Collection

In carrying out this research study, a letter of introduction was obtained from the Department of Science Education Adamawa State University Mubi. The researcher then administered the instrument directly to the respondents which was collected back immediately after completion. The score obtained from the instrument were then analyzed using chi-square.

The statistical test is $(x^2) = \frac{\sum (O-E)^2}{E}$

Where:

O = Observed frequencies

E = Expected frequencies

\sum = Summation

Method of Data Analysis

The researcher used descriptive statistics such as mean, frequency distribution and percentage analysis in computing data obtained which were presented in a tabular form. The data collected on the socio-economic characteristics (bio-data) of the respondents was calculated by percentage while data collected from the research questions was analyzed by using simple mean statistics.

Results And Discussion

Table 2: Analysis of Gender of the Respondents

Gender	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Male	160	66%
Female	80	34%
Total	240	100

Source: Field work, 2025

Table 2 showed that, out of 240 respondents 160 respondents were male which represents (66%) while female were 80 which represents (34%). This means that males participated more than females in the study.

Table 3: Analysis of Age of the Respondents

Age	Frequency	Percentage (%)
18-29	126	52%
30-39	70	29%
40-49	34	15%
50 and above	10	4%
Total	240	100%

Source: Field work, 2025

Table 3 above showed that among the 240 respondents that participated in the study, 126 respondents are between the age of 18-29 which represent 52%, 70 respondents are between the age of 30-39 which represent 29%, 34 respondents were between the age of 40-49 which represent 15%, 10 respondents were between the age of 50 and above which represent 4%. This means that the respondents that are between the age of 18-29 participated more in the study.

Table 4: Analysis of Marital Status of the Respondents

Marital Status	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Married	60	25%
Single	124	51%
Divorced	36	15%
Widow	20	9%
Total	240	100%

Table 4 above showed that, out of 240 respondents, 60 respondents which represented 25% were married. 124 respondents which represent 51% were single, 36 respondents which represents 15% were divorced, while 20 respondents which represents 9% were widow. This showed that, respondents who were Single are the majority of those who participated in the study.

Table 5: Analysis of Educational Qualification of the Respondents

Educational Qualification	Frequency	Percentage (%)
OND/HND	30	13%
NCE/B.Sc/B.A	42	18%
B. Sc Ed/B.Ed	40	16%
Students	120	50%
Others	8	3%
Total	240	100

Source: Field work, 2025

Table 5 above showed that out of 240 respondents, 30 respondents which represent 13% were OND/HND holders, 42 respondents which represent 18% of the respondents were NCE holders. 40 Respondents which represent 16% were B.Sc Ed/B. A, 120 respondents which represent 50% were students, while respondents which have other qualification apart from those mentioned were 8 which represented 3%.

Table 6: Analysis of Years of Experience of the Respondents

Years of Working Experience	Frequency	Percentage (%)
0-5	125	52%
6-10	60	25%
11-19	40	17%
20 and above	15	6%
Total	240	100

Source: Field work, 2025

Table 6 above showed that, out of 240 respondents who participate in the study, respondents have working experience of between 0-5 years were 125 which represent 52%. Respondents that have working experience of 6-10 years were 60 which represent 25%, respondents, and respondents that have working experience of 11-19 were 40 represent 17%, Respondents that have working experience of 20 and above were 15 represent 6% This showed that, majority of the respondents that participated in the study have 0-5 years of working experience.

Table 7: What are the factors affecting the conduct of SSCE as perceived by teachers and students?

S/N	STATEMENT	SA	A	SD	D	Mean	Remark
1	Late arrival of examination materials to the examination hall.	95	65	42	38	2.9	Agreed
2	The school organised extra Moral classes in Preparation to SSCE examination.	60	88	40	52	2.6	Agreed
3	Tine constraints affect the conduct of SSCE examination	40	24	80	96	2.0	Disagreed
4	The school organised practical classes in preparation to SSCE examination.	48	48	56	88	2.2	Disagreed

Table 7 above showed that item (1) ($N=240$, $\bar{X} = 2.9 > 2.5$) which mean that the respondents agreed that Late arrival of examination materials to the examination hall, is one of the problems affecting conduct of examination in secondary schools. This is because the calculate mean of the respondents which is 2.9 is greater than the calculated mean of the rating scale which is 2.5 Item (2) showed that ($N=240$, $\bar{X} = 2.6 > 2.5$) means respondents agreed that; The School organised extra moral classes in preparation to SSCE examination. This is because the calculate mean of the respondents which is 2.6 is greater than the calculated mean of the rating scale which is 2.5.

Item (3) showed ($N=240$, $\bar{X} = 2.0 < 2.5$) means respondents disagreed that; Time constraints affect the conduct of SSCE examination This is because the calculate mean of the respondents which is 2.0 is less than the calculated mean of the rating scale which is 2.5. Item (4) showed that ($N=240$, $\bar{X} = 2.2 < 2.5$) means that; The School organised practical classes in preparation to SSCE examination. This is because the calculate mean of the respondents which is 2.2 is less than the calculated mean of the rating scale which is 2.5.

TABLE 8: Are the examination centres conducive for students writing examination?

S/N	STATEMENT	SA	A	SD	D	Mean	Remark
1	Most of the SSCE examination centres used to be over crowded with Students.	70	90	32	48	2.7	Agree
2	Most of the centres for SSCE examinations are not conducive	100	60	36	44	2.9	Agree
3	Inadequate arrangement of Seats for the conduct of SSCE examination.	22	48	80	90	2.0	Disagree
4	Inadequate funding to conduct SSCE examination.	100	80	30	30	3.0	Agree

Item (1) in table 4.3.2 above showed that; (N=240, $\bar{X} = 2.7 > 2.5$). This means that the respondents agreed that; Most of the SSCE examination centres used to be over crowded with Students, this is because the calculated mean of the respondents which is 2.7 is greater than the calculated mean of the rating scale which is 2.5. Item (2) showed that (N=240, $\bar{X} = 2.9 > 2.5$); means the respondents agreed that; Most of the centres for SSCE examination are not conducive. This is because the calculated mean of the respondents which is 2.9 is greater than the calculated mean of the rating scale which is 2.5

Item (3) showed that; (N=240, $\bar{X} = 2.0 < 2.5$) means the respondents disagreed that; Inadequate arrangement of Seats for the conduct of SSCE examination. This is because the calculate mean of the respondents which is 2.0 is less than the calculated mean of the rating scale which is 2.5. Item (4) showed that (N=240, $\bar{X} = 3.0 > 2.5$) means that the respondents agreed that; Inadequate funding to conduct SSCE examination. This is because the calculated mean of the respondents which is 3.0 is greater than the calculated mean of the rating scale which is 2.5.

TABLE 9: Do invigilators perceived their remuneration as adequate and promptly paid?

S/N	STATEMENT	SA	A	SD	D	Mean	Remark
1	Supervisors and examiners are not adequately paid.	72	80	40	40	2.8	Agree
2	Late payment of the examiners	76	92	36	36	3.0	Agree
3	Most Supervisors collect bribe from the Students.	22	36	92	90	1.9	Disagree
4	During SSCE examination Most invigilators Sell question papers to Students	80	90	30	40	2.8	Agree

Item (1) in table 4.3.4 above showed that (N=240, $\bar{X} = 2.8 > 2.5$) means the respondents agreed that; Supervisors and examiners are not adequately paid. This is because the calculated mean of the respondents which is 2.8 is greater than the calculated mean of the rating scale which is 2.5. Item (2) showed that; (N=240, $\bar{X} = 3.0 > 2.5$) means that; There is late payment of the examiners, This is because the calculated mean of the respondents which is 3.0 is greater than the calculated mean of the rating scale which is 2.5.

Item (3) showed that; (N=240, $\bar{X} = 1.9 < 2.5$) means that the respondents disagreed that; Most Supervisor collect bribe from the students. This is because the calculated mean of the respondents which is 1.9 is less than the calculated mean of the rating scale which is 2.5. Item (4) showed that; (N=240, $\bar{X} = 2.8 < 2.5$) means that during SSCE examination most invigilators sell question papers to students, this is because the calculated mean of the respondents which is 2.8 is greater than the calculated mean of the rating scale which is 2.5.

TABLE 10: Do teachers and students perceive SSCE invigilation is effectively carried out?

S/N	STATEMENT	SA	A	SD	D	Mean	Remark
1	Supervisors conduct SSCE examination very well.	80	96	46	18	2.9	Agreed
2	Supervisors do not allow malpractice during SSCE examination.	30	30	100	80	2.0	Disagreed
3	The supervisors are too careless in supervision.	60	100	40	40	2.7	Agreed
4	There is lack of School Principals full support for the proper conduct of SSCE examination.	75	99	38	28	2.9	Agreed

Item (1) showed that; (N=240, $\bar{X} = 2.9 > 2.5$) the respondents agreed that; Supervisors conduct SSCE examination very well, this is because the calculated mean of the respondents which is 2.9 is greater than the calculated mean of the rating scale which is 2.5. Item (2) showed that; (N=240, $\bar{X} = 2.0 < 2.5$) means the respondents disagreed that; The supervisors do not allow malpractice during SSCE examination, this is because the calculated mean of the respondents which is 2.0 is less than the calculated mean of the rating scale which is 2.5.

Item (3) showed that; (N=240, $\bar{X} = 2.7 > 2.5$) means the respondents agreed that; the supervisors are too careless in supervision, this is because the calculated mean of the respondents which is 2.7 is greater than the calculated mean of the rating scale which is 2.5. Item (4) showed that; (N=240, $\bar{X} = 2.9 > 2.5$) means that the respondents agreed, when they were asked; There is lack of school principals full support for the Proper conduct of SSCE examination. This is because the calculated mean of the respondents which is 2.9 is greater than the calculated mean of the rating scale which is 2.5.

Summary

Summary of the major findings are as follows:

- a) The respondents agreed that the major factors affecting the conduct of SSCE included: overcrowding of examination centres and carelessness of supervisors, late arrival of examination materials, selling of question papers to Students.
- b) Lack of school Principals full Support for the proper conduct of SSCE is also a contributing factor that is affecting the conduct of SSCE.
- c) Inadequate and late payment of supervisor and examiners makes the supervisors to collect bribe and allow malpractice during SSCE.

Conclusion

At the end of the research work, the research was able to reach a conclusion that some factors that contribute to the misconduct of SSCE in our secondary schools include; inadequate and late payment of supervisors and examiners, there is lack of school principals full support for the proper conduct of SSCE. These call for necessary measures that will help to minimize and eradicate the problem.

Recommendations

The research made the following recommendations;

- 1) Governments should adequately pay supervisors and examiners so that they will be serious on supervising examination and avoid collecting bribe.
- 2) Government and Schools Management should also provide conducive examination hall, adequate examination equipment to the schools.
- 3) There is need for government to organize workshop, and seminar for examination supervisors to increase their knowledge and skills so that they can do their job better.

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